

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

EuroGO-SHIP Impact Video

Deliverable 6.5

30-November 2025

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

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About this document

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Dissemination Level

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<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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1. Introduction

The EuroGO-SHIP project brought together 14 partners to work towards enabling the European community conducting hydrographic observations at sea to provide higher quality and more sustainable data flows to a broad range of end users, more effectively. The project demonstrated how to strengthen European capabilities to deliver world-class oceanographic science, which is key to inform policies and to meet the goals of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and the wider objectives of the EU Green Deal.

To encapsulate the many success stories and results of the project and highlight the impact it has had through consultations with the ship-based hydrography communities around Europe, a legacy video was planned, produced and delivered as a 5:40 minute short documentary.

The video was first screened at the Final Event on the 5th of November 2025 in Brussels, Belgium, to an audience of stakeholders including funders and marine Research Infrastructure representatives as well as members of the consortium team. Its second screening was at the project webinar held online on the 20th of November 2025. It was then published on YouTube and promoted on social media.

It can be viewed via this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m1UsoOSBKZ0>

2. Impact Video

2.1. Objectives

The video successfully delivers on the following objectives, as described in the proposal:

- Convey the key results and outcomes of the project,
- Showcase insights and stories from key partners and stakeholders,
- Reflect the results and impact achieved through the implementation of the action,
- Convey key messages, summing up the science case and potential for a EuroGO-SHIP Research Infrastructure and/or services,
- Have a run-time between 3-5 minutes.

2.2. Design Brief

The visual style and editorial tone for the video comply with the project branding, defined in the Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination (CED) Plan (D6.3). One of the major storytelling strategies has been to keep the voice of the scientists (members of the consortium) front and centre, highlighting their expertise and personalities. For this reason, the legacy video features internal team members as narrators rather than engaging an omniscient voice over actor. Compelling photographs of team collaboration were selected

and highlighted to demonstrate the project’s overall objective to shape a new Research Infrastructure through a co-design strategy.

With many achievements in the project and multiple success stories to share, which required exceeding the five-minute target, it was important to apply engaging editing and music to keep the tempo flowing.

2.3. Script Development

The script was developed by partner Seascope Belgium (SSBE). Project key messaging was gleaned from the CED Plan (D6.3) and the Statement of Requirements (D2.5) as well as from final interviews with consortium members offering personal perspectives and insights. The narrative was structured around the three pillars of the project: consultation, demonstration and co-design. It featured testimonials of specific pilot activities towards advancing best practices, as well as overviews of achievements. The beginning of the video introduces the concept of ship-based hydrography, what its contributions are to society and why it is important to support the community conducting it.

The script was delivered to NORCE for review and approved before production commenced.

2.4. Featured Players

Appearing in the video are team members who were interviewed during the First Annual Meeting (June 2023) in Constanta, Romania, and at other opportune times during 2024 and 2025. See section 2.5 for information on who conducted the interviews.

Interviewee	Partner	Location of Shoot	Date
Marta Álvarez	IEO-CSIC	Constanta, Romania -1st AM	Jun 23
Sorin Balan	GeoEcoMar	Constanta, Romania -1st AM	Jun 23
Yvonne Firing	NOC	Southampton, UK	Oct 25
Johannes Karstensen	GEOMAR	Kiel, Germany	Aug 25
Martin Kramp	WMO	Constanta, Romania -1st AM	Jun 23
Pascale Lherminier	IFREMER	Paris, France	Sep 25
Elaine McDonagh	NORCE	Southampton, UK	Oct 25
Emmanuel Salmon	ICOS ERIC	Antwerpen, Belgium	Sep 25
Richard Sanders	NORCE	Galway, Ireland	Oct 23
Katrin Schroeder	CNR	Constanta, Romania -1st AM	Jun 23
Ryan Weber	NORCE	Constanta, Romania -1st AM	Jun 23
Research Infrastructure Representatives/External to EuroGO-SHIP			
Holger Brix	EuroGOOS	Venice, Italy, RI Workshop	Jun 24
Yann-Hervé De Roeck	Euro-Argo ERIC	Venice, Italy, RI Workshop	Jun 24
Ingrid Puillad	EMSO-ERIC	Venice, Italy, RI Workshop	Jun 24

2.4.1. Supporting Players

Many consortium team members and wider community stakeholders appear both in the background of video footage and in photographs that were taken at annual meetings or workshops.

2.4.2. Media Consent

Featured players signed a media consent form and approved the video and their appearance in it before it was screened and posted publicly. Supporting players all indicated they understood their image could be used in promotional material and provided consent via sign-in sheets to the respective events and were reminded orally. Signed forms are on file with SSBE and copies have been delivered to the project archive.

2.5 Assets and Acknowledgements

Visual assets used in the video include live interview footage, B-Roll footage from EuroGO-SHIP meetings, stock footage licensed from Envato Elements, stock footage provided by partners (see list below), animation, and graphics. In addition, maps and photographs were used to support key messaging; these were produced by partners. All assets have been lawfully used. Audio assets are from the Envato Elements catalogue, correctly licensed to the EuroGO-SHIP project.

Video Footage

- MI: Research Vessel (RV) Celtic Explorer, Glider deployed during the Ocean Climate Survey (2021), training video, (Conductivity-Temperature-Depth training video and marine training footage)
- NOC: footage of the rapid NOC video and salinity training activity
- GeoEcoMar, PML, CSIC and GEOMAR: marine training footage
- Stock footage from Envato Elements catalogue - all the video footage is correctly licensed to the EuroGO-SHIP project.

Photographs

- CSIC: pictures of the salinometer
- MI: visuals of the heatmaps
- Met Office: Ocean Forecasting System and Sir David Attenborough (SDA) graphics
- NORCE: map of hydrography activity in Europe
- GEOMAR: picture of Johannes Karstensen and Sorin Balan
- Group pictures by: Liisa Ikonen (ICOS), Anaïs Dyckmans, Julia Falvey (SSBE)

2.6 Production Team

The video was produced by SSBE. The in-house team conducted all bespoke filming, animation, graphics, audio production, and professional editing. All interviews were conducted by SSBE except for Elaine McDonagh and Yvonne Firing, who were filmed by NOC in Southampton, with SSBE providing virtual direction through a Zoom room.

3. Appendix

3.1. EuroGO-SHIP Partners

No.	Short name	Partner organisation name	Country
1	NORCE	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	Norway
2	PML	Plymouth Marine Laboratory	UK
3	CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Italy
4	Ifremer	Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer	France
5	MI	Marine Institute	Ireland
6	NOC	National Oceanography Centre	UK
7	UKMO	Met Office	UK
8	GEOMAR	Helmholtz-Zentrum Für Ozeanforschung Kiel	Germany
9	SSBE	Seascope Belgium	Belgium
10	WMO	World Meteorological Organization	Switzerland
11	ICOS ERIC	Integrated Carbon Observation System European Research Infrastructure Consortium	Finland
12	UiB	Universitetet i Bergen	Norway
13	CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas	Spain
14	GeoEcoMar	Institutul Național de Cercetare – Dezvoltare pentru Geologie și Geoecologie Marină	Romania

3.2. Legacy Video Script

EuroGO-SHIP Legacy Video

Jula Falvey/Anaïs Dyckmans (SSBE)

Final Draft 15-September 2025

Abbreviation Key

VO/Narration: Off camera voice over

OC: We see the interviewee on camera.

OC/Intercut: Interviewee on camera and with voice over B/Roll or conceptual graphics.

B/Roll: background footage for ambient, to support the narrative and/or to illustrate topics being discussed in the interviews

Outline

Sequence 1: [What is hydrography, how does it support society? Intro EuroGO-SHIP](#)

Sequence 2: [Consultation](#)

Sequence 3: [Demonstrations of Concepts and Results](#)

Sequence 4: [Summary/Co-Design New RI Vision](#)

Script

[Fade In]

We see RVs at sea, CTD rosettes, hydrography in action as we hear.

ELAINE (VO/Narration)

Ship-based hydrography is the oldest and most reliable form of ocean observation. It involves deploying instruments from a research vessel and collecting water samples at various depths to analyse ocean physical and chemical properties.

We see Elaine, text overlay of her stats: Dr. Elaine McDonagh, NORCE, EuroGO-SHIP Project Coordinator

ELAINE (OC/VO/Narration)

Data from ship-based hydrography leads to clearer climate change detection, to improving our understanding of ocean carbon, better weather forecasting, and well-informed decision making to protect the ocean ecosystem.

We see Pascale; stats overlay.

PASCALE (OC)

We need data from ship-based hydrography and we need to support the communities in Europe that are producing it.

Text on Screen: key stats: Horizon Europe, 14 partners/logos in swirl, Dec 2022 to Nov 2025 - Emphasis on Co-Designed Strategy from the infographic

ELAINE (OC/VO)

The EuroGO-SHIP project kicked off in late 2022 with 14 partners coming together to shape a new research infrastructure through a co-design strategy.

We see Ryan; stats overlay (intercut with infographic)

RYAN (OC/VO)

To bring Hydrographers together from different countries in Europe and join forces to work together to share equipment, to develop best practices, to work on training and data quality and verification.

RICHARD (OC)

To work out a model for supporting hydrographic observations within the context of other research infrastructures so that Hydrographers can deliver better data to end users at lower cost

[insert the RI map from website]

We see Katrin, stats overlay

KATRIN (OC)

We realized that there was a gap in European landscape of research infrastructures and this was concerning the ship-based Hydrography. The main aim of this project is to find out which are the needs of the community doing this kind of measurement in the European Seas.

Sequence 2: Consultation

ELAINE (OC/VO/ Narration)

At the heart of EuroGO-SHIP has been the consultation activities with regional hydrography networks and the end-users of ocean observation data.

PASCALE (OC)

The participation and support has been inspiring.

Intercut visuals on pen-picture; show survey social med post

ELAINE (OC/VO)

Together, we've developed a quantitative map of where hydrographic activity is taking place within Europe, which did not exist when we started this project.

Intercut below with images from meetings

ELAINE (con't)

We've fostered dialogue within groups which has resulted in joint cruises and knowledge sharing.

Intercut with visuals from the RI workshop and graphics from report document showing services.

ELAINE (con't)

And we hosted an unprecedented Research Infrastructure workshop, with 16 marine RIs participating in activities to get a view of their services, where the EuroGO-SHIP RI would fit, and how the collective landscape could work together to respond to societal challenges.

Each participant with stats overlay.

INGRID PULLAT (OC)

Today I was very happy to attend the EuroGO-SHIP workshop.

We see Holger, with stats and then intercut with Venice Workshop b/roll

HOLGER BRIX (OC/VO)

This meeting was an excellent opportunity to see how these different RI work together.

YANN-HERVÉ De Roeck (OC)

It's, the first of its kind. And I wish the best, of course, for EuroGO-SHIP.

Sequence 3: Demonstrations of concepts

Visuals - key infographic showing the concepts

PASCALE (OC/VO/Narration)

Another success in EuroGO-SHIP was our objective to demonstrate how the delivery of accurate data can be improved through best practices and coordinated service models.

We see the whole infographic with motion towards **Best Practices**

We See Johannes; stats overlay and intercut with footage from the BP KER videos - Yvonne, Tobias, Malcolm...

JOHANNES (OC/VO)

We picked some critical activities, a calibration of some salinometers for example, and also data quality control procedures as our test cases for best practices generation.

MARTIN (OC)

We have the motivation in EuroGO-SHIP to agree as a community on the really best practice, and to become a benchmark at international level.

JOHANNES (OC/VO)

It was really a success also within EuroGO-SHIP that the right ingredients were put together. We had this exchange on shared facilities,

We see the infographic highlights on **Access to Shared Facilities** and **Training**

We See Marta; text overlay and intercut from previous vid.

MARTA (OC/VO)

I loaned our salinometer, you know, is a very big equipment. So it when it traveled from Spain to Romania, I was a little bit afraid of that, but everything went finally smoothly.

SORIN (OC/VO)

I was very glad because I really think we need such equipment, it is important to have more precise measurements.

Intercut over Ivonne (stats overlay) a beat of the water sampling video and flip book style of the KER training videos.

YVONNE (OC/VO)

We've seen improved observations as a result of our pilot activities; and we developed training videos to share with our wider community (pause) so they can improve their data too.

We see the infographic with motion towards **Data Management and Quality Control**

PASCALÉ (OC/VO)

During our data management work, we discovered broken data stream pathways from ship to data centres. And we fixed them. We've helped institutes to adopt a process to transfer real time CTD data from their RVs that will improve ocean and weather forecasts. We've also updated a software system for primary control that will make quality control much easier to implement. So, many successes for EuroGO-SHIP.

Sequence 4 : Summary and Co-Designed New RI Vision

EMMANUEL (OC)

The project has demonstrated that there are services that are needed from the community and that are not provided or not provided in, satisfactory way at the moment. So there is a need for something which is more sustained, more cohesive, more, consistent. And we hope that EuroGO-SHIP will be able to deliver this in the future.

Intercut the value chain graphic as we hear Elaine

ELAINE - (OC/VO)

We've synthesised all of our results to shape the future EuroGO-SHIP RI. And it's poised to become a cornerstone of oceanographic research.

We see text animation and images from deliverables as we hear,

ELAINE (Con't)

Building on the work we've started, it will ensure high-quality data, foster collaboration, and support innovative methodologies and technologies, aligning with EU and global initiatives.

We see logos and text of the initiatives, followed by the group picture from each of the three annual meetings.

ELAINE (Con't)

And through its evolution, members of the EuroGO-SHIP consortium will continue to champion services required to really help us get a more accurate picture of what is going on in our ocean and climate.

Closing credits - teaser for next phase of the project in the near future..

End credits: partner logos, project information, contact details, credits and acknowledgments for assets and participation.

[end]